

**PARTICIPATION OF THE DEFENSE ATTORNEY IN THE
EXAMINATION OF EVIDENCE RELATED TO STATE SECRETS**

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Abstract This article investigates the legal foundations and practical challenges of a defense attorney's participation in examining evidence related to state secrets within the criminal process. Specifically, it analyzes the existing restrictions in Article 89 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their impact on the accused's right to defense. Based on a comparative study of views from scholars like G.Z. Tulaganova and F.M. Mukhitdinov, as well as the legislation of Russia and Germany, the author justifies the expediency of the defense attorney's participation based solely on a non-disclosure agreement, without requiring special clearance. The study concludes with a proposal to amend the national legislation accordingly.

Keywords: State secrets, defense attorney, examination of evidence, Article 89 of CPC, qualified legal aid, adversarial principle, non-disclosure agreement, judicial-legal reforms.

Research Methods: The article employs formal-legal and systemic-structural analysis to elucidate the relationship between the protection of state secrets and the right to defense in criminal proceedings, specifically addressing the existing legal gaps in Article 89 of the CPC. Comparative-legal analysis is used to compare the advanced legislation of foreign countries, such as the Russian Federation and Germany, as well as international standards, with national legislation. Furthermore, logical generalization, synthesis, and deduction methods are utilized in grouping the scientific views of legal scholars, critically examining them, and formulating final proposals for improving legislation.

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Introduction Ensuring a reasonable balance between the need to protect state secrets and the accused's right to defense in criminal proceedings is one of the most complex and pressing legal issues in modern criminal procedural law. On one hand, the inviolability of state secrets requires a strict restriction of access to information; on the other hand, the authority to examine evidence, which is an integral part of human rights, demands transparency and openness in the procedural process.

It is exactly these complex procedural relations that find their legal solution in Article 89 of the Criminal Procedure Code (CPC) of the Republic of Uzbekistan, titled “Protection of State Secrets”. This norm establishes a strict procedural order for conducting inspections, seizures, and other investigative actions within a criminal case involving items, documents, and modern electronic data that constitute state secrets.

The first and second parts of this article stipulate that in order to conduct investigative actions related to state secrets, the prosecutor or the presiding judge must coordinate the time, place, and other conditions of such actions with the head of the enterprise, institution, or organization responsible for storing these items, documents, or electronic data.

However, an analysis of the third part of Article 89 shows that the legislator has artificially restricted the circle of persons who may participate in these specific investigative actions requiring strict compliance with the secrecy regime. Specifically, the norm states: “In conducting such actions, only persons who have clearance to familiarize themselves with items, documents, and electronic data constituting state secrets shall participate as experts, specialists, or attesting witnesses (kholis)”.

Noticeably, this list does not include one of the most important participants in the criminal process — the defense attorney (advocate). In practice, this creates a serious legal collision: if an investigative action involves state secrets and the

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advocate does not have special clearance, they may be excluded from the process of examining evidence.

However, the accused's right to receive qualified legal assistance is a constitutional norm, the realization of which cannot be blocked by administrative restrictions (such as the lack of clearance).

Main Body and Scholarly Views

To confirm this point, it is appropriate to analyze the opinions expressed by various scholars.

Russian scholar V.N. Grigoryev takes a strict position on this matter, arguing: “The professional status of an advocate does not exempt him from the obligation of confidentiality before the state. If the defense attorney does not have clearance for state secrets, the accused must choose another advocate who has such clearance” [1].

In our opinion, this approach cannot be agreed with. The reason is that the accused's right to be defended by an advocate of their own choice is a constitutional guarantee, which cannot be hindered by any restrictions, such as the pretext of a clearance requirement. Furthermore, our research revealed that in practice, the number of advocates with clearance to state secrets is extremely limited, depriving the accused of the opportunity to choose. Additionally, the professional status of an advocate inherently imposes an obligation to maintain confidentiality, and severe liability, up to the deprivation of advocate status, is envisaged for violating this obligation. Finally, this approach violates the adversarial principle; in such a case, procedural equality is disrupted, potentially leading to a subordinate position of the defense compared to the prosecution.

U.A. Tukhtashev also believes in this regard that “It is expedient for the authorized body to grant the advocate a temporary special status (one-time clearance) to familiarize himself with the case materials” [2], while I.L. Petrukhin

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proposes implementing such participation “under the strict control of the judge and only in a closed court session” [3].

We partially agree with the scientific views of these scholars. Both authors do not advocate for the absolute exclusion of the defense attorney from the process of examining evidence related to state secrets but rather propose that their participation must be ensured through a certain procedural order. This is a significantly progressive view compared to the outdated approach that completely denies the right to defense.

At the same time, a number of problematic aspects may arise in the practical application of these proposals. In particular, although the mechanism of “temporary special status” proposed by U.A. Tukhtashev seems theoretically acceptable, in practice, obtaining it requires complex and lengthy bureaucratic processes. As a result, the defense attorney may be deprived of the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the evidence in a timely manner, which will inevitably have a negative impact on the quality of the defense.

As for I.L. Petrukhin's proposal of acting “under the strict control of the judge and only in a closed court session,” its scope is mainly limited to the trial stage. However, the process of examining evidence is primarily carried out at the preliminary investigation stage, and it is at this very stage that the active participation of the defense attorney is of decisive importance. Therefore, this proposal is unable to fill the legal gap at the preliminary investigation stage. Thus, while the scientific views of these scholars are an important step towards solving the problem, their proposals are insufficient to fully and effectively ensure the participation of the defense attorney in the process of examining evidence.

G.Z. Tulaganova rightfully emphasizes: “The principle of equality of arms in criminal proceedings cannot be violated under the pretext of protecting state secrets. Excluding an advocate from an investigative action due to the lack of a special

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clearance is a gross violation of the right to defense. It is sufficient to take a non-disclosure receipt (agreement) from the advocate” [4]. Similarly, F.M. Mukhitdinov noted that “Restricting the advocate's powers in the process of proof with administrative barriers (clearance) contradicts the spirit of the Criminal Procedure Code” [5], and Yu.S. Pilipenko provides a firm conclusion: “When an advocate enters a case containing a state secret, he automatically assumes the obligation to keep the secret. Additional verification by security agencies is not required” [6].

In our opinion, the scientific views of the aforementioned scholars represent the most optimal legal solution to this problem. Indeed, as G.Z. Tulaganova emphasized, the constitutional foundation of the criminal process—the principle of equality of arms and adversarial proceedings—should not be sacrificed under the pretext of protecting state secrets.

Also, relying on the positions of F.M. Mukhitdinov and Yu.S. Pilipenko, it can be stated that the special status of an advocate and their legal professional responsibility are sufficient guarantees for preserving state secrets. Restricting it with additional administrative barriers (clearance) contradicts the essence of the Criminal Procedure Code. Therefore, by introducing a mechanism for taking a written obligation (receipt) of non-disclosure of state secrets from the defense attorney, it is possible to fully ensure both the interests of state security and the accused's right to defense simultaneously.

Comparative Analysis In order to find a legal solution to the theoretical problems noted above, it is expedient to conduct a comparative analysis of the advanced criminal procedural legislation of foreign countries.

Specifically, Part 5 of Article 49 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation clearly defines the mechanism for a defense attorney working with state secrets. According to it, if a criminal case contains state secrets and the advocate does not have a special clearance, their removal from the case is not

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permitted. In such a situation, only a receipt of non-disclosure of state secrets is taken from the defense attorney, and they have the right to fully participate in the process of examining evidence [7]. This experience shows that to ensure security, it is not necessary to exclude the advocate from the process; enhancing their professional responsibility is sufficient.

In contrast, according to Paragraph 147 of the German StPO (CPC), the defense attorney has the right to unhindered access to case materials. Regarding materials containing state secrets, the defense attorney has the right to view, study, compare, and analyze them. There is no requirement for special clearance in Germany—the professional status of the defense attorney is considered sufficient [8].

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has paid special attention to the balance between state secrets and the right to defense in its case law. According to the Court's established position, based on the requirements of Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights, national security interests can never serve as a basis for completely negating the accused's right to examine the evidence used against them.

In particular, in the case of *Edwards and Lewis v. the United Kingdom*, the court concluded: “If evidence is concealed from the defense under the pretext of protecting state secrets or public interests, and the defense attorney is deprived of the opportunity to examine it, such a process cannot be considered a fair trial. Even under the strictest conditions of secrecy, the defense attorney must be provided with minimal procedural guarantees to familiarize himself with the evidence” [9].

The analyses carried out during the research show that ensuring a balance between the protection of state secrets and the right to examine evidence in the criminal procedural legislation of Uzbekistan is an urgent task today. The advanced experience of countries such as Germany and Russia, as well as the international

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law standards examined above, confirm that the secrecy regime should not be grounds for artificially excluding the defense side from the process of proof.

Conclusion and Proposals Based on the results of the comparative-legal and theoretical analyses conducted above, in order to fill this procedural gap in our national legislation, the following scientific conclusion can be formulated: The most effective mechanism for ensuring the participation of the defense attorney in cases involving state secrets, which aligns with the principles of fair justice, is to fully involve them in the process of examining evidence by obtaining a receipt of non-disclosure of state secrets from them.

Based on the above, we propose to amend the third part of Article 89 of the CPC of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

"In conducting such actions, an expert, specialist, attesting witness (kholis), as well as a defense attorney shall participate. If these persons do not have clearance to work with state secrets, a receipt of non-disclosure of state secrets shall be taken from them, and they shall have the right to fully participate in the process of examining the evidence."

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